

An Electrically Small Planar Antenna

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Introduction

It has been previously shown that it is possible to match an electrically small antenna to a 50-ohm coaxial line by placing a matching post near the base of the antenna [1, 2, 3]. This antenna was designed to fit in a cubical volume. In this investigation we design a planar antenna which is also electrically small, self-resonant and is matched to a 50-ohm coaxial line; it is mounted over a ground plane. It is also much thinner and could be used for closely spaced array elements. It is actually a modification of an inverted – F antenna where an extra set of parallel wires is added to that antenna [1]. In order to achieve the matching, we place an inductance at its endpoint and use a matching post near the input of the antenna, both of which are connected to the ground plane. We conducted simulations of the antenna configuration shown in Fig. 1 for different values of antenna length, width, height, inductance terminations and matching posts. After obtaining satisfactory computational results, we built and tested three of these antennas.

Approach

The antenna simulations, which used the Numerical Electromagnetics Code (NEC-4) [4], were initially done for values of length, l and height, h fixed at 5 cm. The value of h_1 was varied from .4 cm to 1.2 cm, h_2 from 1 cm to 3 cm, w from .5 cm to 2.0 cm, L from .1 to 1.0 μ Henries and α had values of 30°, 45° and 60°. The objective was to find antenna configurations that had a low VSWR when driven from a 50-ohm coaxial line. We simulated an antenna having the following values: $l = 5$ cm, $h = 5$ cm, $w = 1$ cm, $h_1 = 1$ cm, $h_2 = 1$ cm and $\alpha = 30^\circ$ and $L = .55$ μ Henries; the wire diameter was 3/32" (.24 cm). The simulation was done for the antenna over an infinite ground plane. The input impedance, VSWR and radiation pattern were computed. We then built this antenna using 3/32" brass tubing and a wire-wound inductance about 1 cm in length, 0.4 cm in diameter and having a value of 0.55 μ Henries; since the dimensions of the fabricated antenna were slightly different from the original simulation, we redid the simulation using the actual dimensions of the antenna that was built. We also simulated and tested lower profile antennas having approximate lengths, $l = 7$ cm and 9 cm, and heights $h = 4$ cm and 3 cm respectively. Once again, since the fabricated antennas did not have the same exact dimensions as the original simulation we redid these simulations with dimensions that were close to those of the fabricated antennas. The measurements were made with a Hewlett- Packard Model 8510 Network Analyzer with the antenna mounted over a 4ft x 4 ft (1.2 m x 1.2 m) ground plane. The antennas were fed with a Type N connector.

Results

In Fig. 2 we show simulated and measured impedance plots for a planar antenna having the following dimensions: $l = 6.5$ cm, $h = 5.1$ cm, $w = 1.1$ cm, $h_1 = 3.4$ cm, $h_2 = 1.1$ cm, $\alpha = 69^\circ$ and $L = .55$ μ Henries. The solid curve is the simulated antenna and covers the frequency range of 320 MHz to 330 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.10 occurs at a frequency of 325 MHz. The dashed curve is the measured impedance and covers the frequency range from 316 MHz to 325 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.16 occurs at a frequency of 321 MHz. The electrical height of this antenna is $h/\lambda = .055$; the total length of tubing is about $.41\lambda$. The approximate frequency band for which the VSWR was below 2.0 was 1.1% for the simulation and 1.5% for the measurement. The simulated radiation pattern for this antenna had a maximum vertically polarized gain of about 4.3 dB along the horizon and a horizontally polarized gain of about -7 dB in the zenith direction. The radiation pattern was not measured, however for a finite ground plane, it is expected that the peak gain would be at a higher elevation angle.

In Fig. 3 we show simulated and measured impedance plots for a planar antenna having the following dimensions: $l = 7.15$ cm, $h = 4.1$ cm, $w = 1.15$ cm, $h_1 = 2.0$ cm, $h_2 = 1.1$ cm, $\alpha = 53^\circ$ and $L = .55$ μ Henries. The solid curve is the simulated antenna and covers the frequency range of 345 MHz to 355 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.23 occurs at a frequency of 349 MHz. The dashed curve is the measured impedance and covers the frequency range from 355 MHz to 362 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.22 occurs at a frequency of 359 MHz. The electrical height of this antenna is $h/\lambda = .048$; the total length of tubing is about $.38\lambda$. The approximated frequency band for which the VSWR was below 2.0 was 0.8% for the simulation and 0.9% for the measurement. The radiation pattern of this antenna was similar to the previous antenna but it had a slightly higher gain at zenith.

Finally, in Fig. 4 we show simulated and measured impedance plots for a low profile planar antenna having the following dimensions: $l = 9.1$ cm, $h = 3.0$ cm, $w = .7$ cm, $h_1 = 1.4$ cm, $h_2 = .4$ cm, $\alpha = 49^\circ$ and $L = .55$ μ Henries. The solid curve is the simulated antenna and covers the frequency range of 352 MHz to 357 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.29 occurs at a frequency of 354 MHz. The dashed curve is the measured impedance and covers the frequency range from 351 MHz to 357 MHz. A minimum VSWR of 1.04 occurs at a frequency of 354 MHz. The electrical height of this antenna is $h/\lambda = .035$; the total length of tubing is about $.38\lambda$. The approximated frequency band for which the VSWR was below 2.0 was 0.4% for the simulation and 1.0% for the measurement. Once again the radiation pattern of this antenna was similar to those of the previous antennas and as

expected, because it has longer horizontal segments, the gain in the zenith direction was still higher.

The comparison of simulated and measured results is very good considering that the simulation is done for the antenna over an infinite ground plane and with a “point source” inductance, whereas the measurements are made over a finite ground plane with an inductance having a finite size.

Conclusions

We have shown that it is possible to design and fabricate an electrically small inductive loaded planar antenna that is very well matched to a 50-ohm coaxial line. We have shown that there is excellent agreement between simulated and measured results. The design parameters have a lot of flexibility from the standpoint that the planar shape can vary in length, height and width. As is the case for small antennas, these antennas are relatively narrow band; they have a bandwidth of approximately 1% for which the VSWR is below 2.0. If the antenna is made slightly larger, the bandwidth can be increased. The antenna may be made physically smaller if a dielectric slab is inserted between the parallel wires. Also it may be possible to fabricate this antenna on printed circuit board and replace the wire-wound inductor with a smaller surface mount inductor.

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Fig. 1 Planar Antenna

Fig. 2 $l = 6.5$ cm, $h = 5.1$ cm,
 $w = 1.1$ cm

Fig.3 $l = 7.1$ cm, $h = 4.1$ cm
 $w = 1.15$ cm

Fig. 4 $l = 9.1$, $h = 3.0$,
 $w = 0.7$